

Radiation-sensing cosmoreceptors

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DRAFT

Understanding how organisms sense or communicate is a fundamental question in biology. Whether organisms can sense non-electromagnetic radiation is unclear. To provide a unifying term for both electromagnetic radiation-sensing and particle radiation-sensing proteins, I propose cosmoreceptors for protein-based radiation-sensing receptors that include light-sensitive/sensing proteins or protein photoreceptors as well. Examples of cosmoreceptors include cyanobacterium (*Synechocystis*) SynEtr1, a dual gasoreceptor and light-sensitive protein/photoreceptor protein. SynEtr1 can sense ethylene gas and ultraviolet-A radiation and trigger cellular signaling via a kinase domain. Identifying cosmoreceptors in extremophile organisms may allow us to develop radiation-resistant radiation sensors or develop alternate strategies to or supplement radiotherapies.